

ATOMISTIC MODELLING OF CROSSLINKED EPOXY POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

Keywords: Epoxy Resin, Cross-links, Molecular Dynamics, LAMMPS

Molecular Dynamics simulations are used to study cross-linking of a particular epoxy polymer with a cross-linking agent. OPLS force field parameters are used for modeling a 2:1 stoichiometric mixture of epoxy resin and the cross-linking agent. The model has 17,928 united atoms and static cross-linking method is used along with molecular minimization and molecular dynamics techniques in order to achieve four different cross-link densities. The cross-linked models can be used for understanding various phenomenon occurring in real cross-linked epoxy resins at the atomic scale.

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy Resins are prime constituents in adhesives, sealants, and aircraft composite structural components. A wide range of studies have focused on epoxy-based materials to establish physical and mechanical properties [1-3]. The excellent specific-stiffness and specific-strength properties of epoxy-based composite materials are due to the complex microstructure of their constituent materials. There is significant interest in understanding the aging response of these material systems due to their wide-spread use in commercial aircraft.

Epoxy resins are formed when epoxy monomers react with compounds known as cross-linking or curing agents with active hydrogens such as amines and anhydrides [4]. A trial-and-error approach to experimentally optimize the processing conditions of epoxy materials can become time-consuming and expensive. With the advancement of computational technology, computational modeling has provided an efficient route to study these polymer resins [4-15]. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations based on the

bead-spring model [10, 11] and Monte-Carlo simulations based on the bond-fluctuation model [8, 9, 16] have been used in the last two decades for studying epoxy materials. The bead-spring models did not take into account the details of the molecular structures and thus cannot predict the influence of specific groups of atoms on the physical properties. In the last few years, MD at the atomic scale has been quite successful in exploring different phenomena occurring at pico- to nano-second time scales [12]. Many researchers have studied formation of cross-linked epoxy resins by using different approaches of simulated cross-linking. Doherty et al. [5] modeled PMA networks using lattice-based simulations in a polymerization MD scheme. Yarovsky and Evans [13] discussed a cross-linking technique which they used to crosslink low molecular-weight, water-soluble, phosphate-modified epoxy resins (CYMEL 1158). The cross-linking reactions were carried out simultaneously (static cross-linking process). Dynamic cross-linking of epoxy resins was performed by Xu et al. [4]. Their model was used to study the diffusion of water in these cross-linked networks. An iterative Molecular Dynamics/Molecular Minimization (MM) procedure was used to cross-link an epoxy resin (DGEBA), with one cross-link established per iteration. Other computational studies [6, 17] involving cross-linking of epoxies have been performed. All of the studies discussed thus far were performed on relatively small model systems (less than 2200 atoms in all the studies). Heine et al. simulated large PDMS networks using a dynamic cross-linking approach [7] and Varshney et al. [12] used Heine's dynamic cross-linking approach and Xu's MD/MM concept [4] to cross-link EPON862 with DETDA. Varshney et al. [12] modeled two different systems having molecules of EPON and DETDA in the ratios of 128:64 (EPON: DETDA) and 256:128. Although dynamic approaches to establishing crosslinks may provide a more realistic physical understanding of the crosslinking process than static crosslinking, it is more difficult to control the ultimate cross-link density of a molecular model using dynamic approaches. Also, because cross-linking can occur on relatively large time scales (e.g. minutes), MD-based dynamic approaches may not be ideal for simulating the cross-linking process. Therefore, a static approach to crosslinking large molecular models of epoxy is necessary to efficiently establish such models for parametric studies involving multiple, pre-defined cross-link densities.

The objective of this study was to establish a method of statically cross-linking large systems of EPON and DETDA molecules having a molecular ratio of 432:216. In this method, the MD/MM techniques used by Varshney et al. [12] for establishing an EPON-DETDA modeled structure with a 2:1 molecular ratio was coupled with the static cross-linking method described by Yarovsky and Evans [13]. A description of the modeling procedure for a monomer solution is followed by a description of the cross-linking mechanism. Finally, the obtained cross-linking data is compared with that obtained by other researchers.

MODELLING STRUCTURE

The initial structure consists of the EPON-862 monomer (Di-glycidyl ether of Bisphenol-F) and a cross-linking agent named as DETDA (Diethylene Toluene Diamine). EPON-862 is produced by Hexion Chemicals Inc. The molecules of EPON-862 and DETDA are shown in Figure 1. A stoichiometric mixture (2:1 ratio) of 2 molecules of EPON-862 and 1 molecule of DETDA was modeled first using the

LAMMPS (Large Scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator) simulation program. LAMMPS is a free MD and molecular minimization software developed by Sandia National Laboratories [18]. The initial atomic coordinates were written in a coordinate file in the native LAMMPS format and the OPLS United Atom force field [19-21] was used for defining the bond, angle, and dihedral parameters. The non-bonded Van Der Waals interactions were modeled using the 12-6 Lennard-Jones potential. By using this particular OPLS United Atom force field, all CH₃, CH₂, and CH groups were modeled as single united atoms with the corresponding masses. The Carbon and Hydrogen atoms of the two benzene rings present in one EPON-862 molecule were considered as single atoms only. Similarly for the DETDA molecule, the Carbon and Hydrogen atoms of the benzene ring and the Nitrogen and Hydrogen atoms present in the amine groups were considered as single atoms only. In the DETDA molecule, the alkyl groups attached to the benzene rings were considered as united atoms. Thus in a 2:1 structure the number of atoms were reduced from 116 atoms to 83 atoms with the use of united atoms.

Figure 1. Molecular Structure of EPON-862 resin and DETDA cross-linking molecules

The initial 2:1 structure was formed in a cubic box which was 10 Angstroms long along each direction with periodic boundary conditions. This structure was subjected to four molecular minimizations (MM) and three MD simulations in order to minimize internal forces (thus reduce internal residual stresses) resulting from the construction of bonds, bond angles, and bond dihedrals. After reaching a relatively low energy value, this structure was replicated to form eight more structures within the simulation box so that a 16:8 molecular mixture of EPON and DETDA monomers was established. A slow stress relaxation procedure was performed over a cycle of 20 MM and 10 MD simulations. All MD simulations were NVT (constant volume and temperature) simulations for 100 ps at 600 K. The NVT ensemble made use of the Nose/Hoover thermostat and barostat for temperature and pressure control, respectively [22]. After every cycle of MD and MM, the box size was reduced by a small amount. After all minimization and MD runs, a final density of 1.213gm/cc was achieved. The final pressure value of the last minimization was less than 1 atmosphere which indicated that the structure had almost no residual stress. This equilibrated structure was used for the subsequent cross-linking step.

The OPLS All-Atom and United Atom force fields were developed by Jorgensen and co-workers [19, 20, 23]. In this force field, the total energy of a molecular system is a sum of all the individual energies associated with bond, angle, dihedral, and 12-6

Lennard Jones deformations. The equilibrium spacing parameter (σ) of the Lennard-Jones potential was taken to be the arithmetic mean of the individual parameters of the respective atom types while the well depth parameter (ε) was taken to be the geometric mean of the values of the respective atom types. The bond energy is given by

$$E_{bond} = \sum_{bonds} K_r (r - r_0)^2 \quad (1)$$

where K_r is a force constant having units of (energy/distance²), r is the distance between the two atoms considered, and r_0 is the equilibrium bond distance. The energy associated with bond-angle bending is

$$E_{angle} = \sum_{angles} K_\theta (\theta - \theta_0) \quad (1)$$

where K_θ is a force constant having units of (energy/radians²), θ is the bond angle, and θ_0 is the equilibrium bond angle. The dihedral potential is given by

$$E_{dihedral} = \frac{V_1}{2}[1 + \cos \phi] + \frac{V_2}{2}[1 - \cos 2\phi] + \frac{V_3}{2}[1 + 3 \cos \phi] + \frac{V_4}{2}[1 - 4 \cos \phi] \quad (1)$$

where V_1 , V_2 , V_3 , and V_4 are coefficients in the Fourier series [19, 21] having units of energy and ϕ is the dihedral angle.

CROSS-LINKING PROCEDURE

The equilibrated structure of 16:8 model was statically cross-linked based on the root mean square (RMS) distance between the Nitrogen atoms of DETDA and CH₂ groups of the EPON molecules [12]. Simultaneous breaking of CH₂-O bonds in the epoxide ends of the EPON molecules and N-H bonds of the DETDA molecules made the CH₂⁺ ends capable of forming cross-links with N²⁻ activated atoms of the DETDA molecules. A particular N²⁻ can form a cross-link with the CH₂⁺ of any adjacent EPON molecule within a cutoff distance. Figures 2 and 3 demonstrate the cross-linking process. Three assumptions were made for the cross-linking process:

- 1) Both primary amines in DETDA were assumed to have the same reactivity
- 2) The CH₂-O and N-H bonds were broken simultaneously (Figure 2)
- 3) A Nitrogen atom was partially activated as NH⁻ when it had only one CH₂⁺ within a defined cutoff distance.

The activation of CH₂⁺, N²⁻ and NH⁻ are shown in Figure 2. Cross-links were formed by computing all RMS distances between each N atom and the CH₂ united atoms within the defined cutoff distance. The cutoff distance was defined as the maximum RMS distance that was chosen to find all possible CH₂⁺ - NH⁻ pairs. The CH₂⁺ radicals located outside the cut-off distance of a particular NH⁻ group were not cross-linked to that particular

group. The H^+ ions formed by the breaking of NH_2 bonds were reacted with the O^- atoms of the broken epoxide ends. This bond formation was also performed based on the closest RMS distances between the O^- and H^+ atoms. The partial cross-linking reaction and the two-step complete cross-linking reaction are shown in Figure 3. Four different cross-linked structures were formed for a range of cutoff distances.

Figure 2. (A) Activation of CH_2^+ from $O-CH_2$, (B) Complete activation of N^{2-} from NH_2 , (C) Partial activation of NH^- from NH_2 . (The wavy lines represent the remaining parts of the EPON and DETDA molecules in the respective structures)

Figure 3. (A) 1st step of cross-linking in a complete cross-linking reaction where N^{2-} is reacted with one EPON molecule, (B) 2nd step of cross-linking reaction where N^{2-} is reacted, (C) Cross-linking of a partially activated amine where NH^- is reacted with an EPON molecule.

After cross-linking, new bond, angle, and dihedral parameters were defined in the structure. The cross-linked 16:8 models were equilibrated by performing one cycle of two minimizations and one MD run alternately to remove the residual stresses generated during the formation of the cross-links. The equilibrated, cross-linked 16:8 models were oriented and translated into 27 more structures and these structures formed large systems that were a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ array of 16:8 structures. The large systems had 432 molecules of EPON and 216 molecules of DETDA. The 27 structures had the same cross-links as those of the original 16:8 model. For four different defined cutoff distances (thus four different cross-link densities), the 16:8 models had differences in

the number of bonds, angles, and dihedrals. In one 16:8 structure, 32 possible cross-linking sites exist. The crosslink density of the polymer was defined as the total number of these sites that were crosslinked. For example, a specimen having 16 out of 32 cross-links was defined as having a 50% cross-link density. Each of these four samples had 17,928 united atoms while the number of modeled individual atoms in each chemical structure was 25,272. At this point it is important to note the advantage of modeling united atoms instead of individual atoms. Simulations can perform more efficiently when fewer atoms are modeled. It is assumed herein that the simulated united atom model will predict bulk-level properties as accurately as an all-atom model. A 432:216 structure having a cross-link density of 50% is shown below in Figure 4.

Figure 4. 432:216 model of EPON-DETDA containing 17,928 united atoms

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using the cross-linking procedure described in the previous section, it was found that a large percentage of cross-links form for cutoff distances between 3 to 4 Angstroms. At less than a 3 Angstroms cutoff, 9 out of 32 cross-links were formed. At less than a 4 Angstroms cutoff, 18 out of 32 cross-links were formed. Therefore, a large increase in cross-link density occurred from 28% to 56% over a range difference of 1 Angstrom. This trend was close to the trend of cross-link densities found by Varshney et al. [12] by using an alternative, dynamic-based cross-linking approach. Because a polymer with a cross-link density less than 40% is too viscous for structural applications, four different cross-link densities were chosen that were equal to and above 50%. The densities were

50% at a 3.8 Angstrom cutoff, 59.375% at a 5 Angstrom cutoff, 71.875% at 8 Angstrom cutoff, and 84.375% at a 10 Angstrom cutoff. Each of these four cross-linked 16:8 models were used to form the four corresponding 432:216 models. Further cross-linking between these 27 systems of 16:8 models were performed once the total 432:216 systems were completely equilibrated. The cross-link graph shown in Figure 5 shows the dependence of the crosslinking density on the crosslinking cutoff distance. The trend of this graph is similar to that obtained by Varshney et al [12]. A steep rise can be seen where the cross-link density increased from just above 15% to almost 60% over a span of a cutoff distance between 2 and 4 Angstroms. Another important aspect of this graph is the plateau over which the cross-link density increased very little over a range of 4 to 8 Angstroms and again after 10 Angstroms. The reason for this behavior of the polymer system is likely because of the nature of the Lennard-Jones potential that was used to establish the initial equilibrium monomer solution.

Figure 5. The dependence of the crosslink density on crosslinking cutoff distance

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by NASA Langley Research Center under the Aging Aircraft Program (Grant NNH06ZEA00IN-AAD2). The authors thank Dr. Thomas C. Clancy and Dr. Sarah-Jane V. Frankland for their input regarding the cross-linking procedure.

REFERENCES

1. Liu, H.P., A. Uhlherr, and M.K. Bannister, *Quantitative structure-property relationships for composites: prediction of glass transition temperatures for epoxy resins*. *Polymer*, 2004. **45**(6): p. 2051-2060.
2. Boinard, P., W.M. Banks, and R.A. Pethrick, *Changes in the dielectric relaxations of water in epoxy resin as a function of the extent of water ingress in carbon fibre composites*. *Polymer*, 2005. **46**(7): p. 2218-2229.
3. Ni, Y., S.X. Zheng, and K.M. Nie, *Morphology and thermal properties of inorganic-organic hybrids involving epoxy resin and polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes*. *Polymer*, 2004. **45**(16): p. 5557-5568.
4. Wu, C.F. and W.J. Xu, *Atomistic molecular modelling of crosslinked epoxy resin*. *Polymer*, 2006. **47**(16): p. 6004-6009.
5. Doherty, D.C., et al., *Polymerization molecular dynamics simulations. I. Cross-linked atomistic models for poly(methacrylate) networks*. *Computational and Theoretical Polymer Science*, 1998. **8**(1-2): p. 169-178.
6. Fan, H.B. and M.M.F. Yuen, *Material properties of the cross-linked epoxy resin compound predicted by molecular dynamics simulation*. *Polymer*, 2007. **48**(7): p. 2174-2178.
7. Heine, D.R., et al., *Atomistic simulations of end-linked poly(dimethylsiloxane) networks: Structure and relaxation*. *Macromolecules*, 2004. **37**(10): p. 3857-3864.
8. Jo, W.H. and M.B. Ko, *Structure Development in Epoxy-Resin Modified with Thermoplastic Polymer - a Monte-Carlo Simulation Approach*. *Macromolecules*, 1993. **26**(20): p. 5473-5478.
9. Jo, W.H. and M.B. Ko, *Effect of Reactivity on Cure and Phase-Separation Behavior in Epoxy-Resin Modified with Thermoplastic Polymer - a Monte-Carlo Simulation Approach*. *Macromolecules*, 1994. **27**(26): p. 7815-7824.
10. Stevens, M.J., *Interfacial fracture between highly cross-linked polymer networks and a solid surface: Effect of interfacial bond density*. *Macromolecules*, 2001. **34**(8): p. 2710-2718.
11. Tsige, M. and M.J. Stevens, *Effect of cross-linker functionality on the adhesion of highly cross-linked polymer networks: A molecular dynamics study of epoxies*. *Macromolecules*, 2004. **37**(2): p. 630-637.
12. Varshney, V., et al., *A molecular dynamics study of epoxy-based networks: Cross-linking procedure and prediction of molecular and material properties*. *Macromolecules*, 2008. **41**(18): p. 6837-6842.
13. Yarovsky, I. and E. Evans, *Computer simulation of structure and properties of crosslinked polymers: application to epoxy resins*. *Polymer*, 2002. **43**(3): p. 963-969.
14. Valavala, P.K., et al., *Nonlinear multiscale modeling of polymer materials*. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2007. **44**(3-4): p. 1161-1179.
15. Valavala, P.K., et al., *Multiscale modeling of polymer materials using a statistics-based micromechanics approach*. *Acta Materialia*, 2009. **57**(2): p. 525-532.
16. Carmesin, I. and K. Kremer, *The Bond Fluctuation Method - a New Effective Algorithm for the Dynamics of Polymers in All Spatial Dimensions*. *Macromolecules*, 1988. **21**(9): p. 2819-2823.

17. Fan, H.B., et al., *Molecular dynamics simulation of thermal cycling test in electronic packaging*. Journal of Electronic Packaging, 2007. **129**(1): p. 35-40.
18. Plimpton, S., *Fast Parallel Algorithms for Short-Range Molecular-Dynamics*. Journal of Computational Physics, 1995. **117**(1): p. 1-19.
19. Jorgensen, W.L., D.S. Maxwell, and J. TiradoRives, *Development and testing of the OPLS all-atom force field on conformational energetics and properties of organic liquids*. Journal of the American Chemical Society, 1996. **118**(45): p. 11225-11236.
20. Weiner, S.J., et al., *A New Force-Field for Molecular Mechanical Simulation of Nucleic-Acids and Proteins*. Journal of the American Chemical Society, 1984. **106**(3): p. 765-784.
21. Watkins, E.K. and W.L. Jorgensen, *Perfluoroalkanes: Conformational analysis and liquid-state properties from ab initio and Monte Carlo calculations*. Journal of Physical Chemistry A, 2001. **105**(16): p. 4118-4125.
22. Hoover, W.G., *Canonical Dynamics - Equilibrium Phase-Space Distributions*. Physical Review A, 1985. **31**(3): p. 1695-1697.
23. Duffy, E.M., P.J. Kowalczyk, and W.L. Jorgensen, *Do Denaturants Interact with Aromatic-Hydrocarbons in Water*. Journal of the American Chemical Society, 1993. **115**(20): p. 9271-9275.